

Tensor Train Decomposition Applied to the Isogeometric Discontinuous Galerkin k -Eigenvalue 2-D Neutron Transport Equation

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ABSTRACT

We demonstrate the application of tensor train (TT) decomposition on the operators of the Discontinuous Galerkin (DG) k -eigenvalue 2-D neutron transport equation (NTE) with higher-order scattering. The equation is discretized using the discrete ordinates method in angle, multigroup in energy, and Isogeometric Analysis (IGA) in space. Our use of IGA enables exact geometric representations of the original CAD model, as demonstrated with a homogenized circle and a cruciform fuel geometry. We compare the TT format's compression with that of the Compressed Sparse Row (CSR) format and validate solutions against analytic or Monte Carlo references. TT achieves operator compression ratios ranging from $10\times$ to $10^5\times$ greater than CSR. However, power iteration with GMRES is $2\times$ to $100\times$ faster with CSR because it cannot exploit the low-rank structure of the operators when using an uncompressed vector. These results suggest that the TT format offers substantial storage savings; however, further work is needed to leverage the low-rank structure in the solver and the solution vector.

Keywords: Discrete Ordinates, Multi-Patch Isogeometric Analysis, Low Rank Approximation, Tensor Networks, Iterative Methods

1. INTRODUCTION

Isogeometric analysis (IGA) [1] offers the ability to map partial differential equations onto computer-aided design (CAD) models directly, obviating the need for computationally expensive meshing schemes that often struggle on complex geometries encountered in some advanced reactor designs. This also enables the neutronics equations to be solved on a consistent geometric representation used by other relevant physics (e.g. heat transport).

The IGA approach flips the traditional Finite Element Analysis (FEA) paradigm, in which a basis for the *unknown* solution field is chosen and then approximately imposed onto the *known* geometry. This new approach, known as the *isoparametric concept*, imposes the basis used in the CAD model onto the solution field. The subsequent IGA meshes are refinement-invariant, exact geometric representations of the CAD model with higher continuity ($\geq C^0$ -continuity). However, this higher continuity results in denser PDE operators, which already scale exponentially with the number of dimensions, $\mathcal{O}(N^d)$. This phenomenon, known as the *curse of dimensionality*, typically necessitates the use of matrix-free inversion methods or sparse matrix formats, such as the Compressed Sparse Row (CSR) format. These sparse formats scale at $\mathcal{O}(\text{number of non-zeros (nnz)})$; however, densification from the increased continuity of IGA meshes potentially compromises their efficiency.

Fields including quantum mechanics [2], computational fluid dynamics (CFD) [3], machine learning [4], and others [4] have turned to tensor networks (TNs) to break the *curse of dimensionality*. Several TN formats have seen extensive application, including the Tucker, tensor train (TT), and hierarchical Tucker

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(HT) formats [4, 5]. The TT decomposition has been applied to the transport of neutrons [6] and thermal radiation [7]. Both applications employed discrete ordinates and diamond-difference approximations, with the neutron transport application focusing exclusively on homogenized Cartesian meshes with isotropic scattering. Both applications demonstrated exceptional compression, especially in the angular dimensions, given the memory complexity of $\mathcal{O}(dNr^2)$ using TT on a d -dimensional tensor. However, the applicability of the TT format to more complex, heterogeneous geometries remains an open research question, with the authors of [6] speculating that diminishing returns may occur as the number of unique materials increases.

In this work, we demonstrate the TT decomposition on the multigroup discrete ordinates k -eigenvalue 2-D NTE with a discontinuous isogeometric spatial discretization. Our applications include a homogenized circle and an infinite array of cruciform fuel inspired by the Lightbridge design. We compare both applications to an analytic or OpenMC reference solution. The TT format applied to the Discontinuous Galerkin (DG) NTE offers superior compression compared to the CSR sparse matrix format. The interior operators demonstrate better compression than the boundary operators due to the rank-1 angular-spatial coupling. However, the CSR format prevails in time-to-solution because the solver cannot leverage the low-rank structure of the operators when using a full solution vector. We show that the compressibility of the solution vector is problem-dependent, with TT-formatted fluxes compressing considerably less than the operators. Future investigations into tensor network topologies for the angular flux could enable more effective exploitation of the operators' low-rank structure.

2. BACKGROUND

The multigroup discrete ordinates time-independent 2-D NTE is

$$\hat{\Omega}_{i_\Omega} \cdot \nabla \psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\mathbf{x}) + \Sigma_{t, i_E}(\mathbf{x}) \psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i'_E=1}^{N_E} \sum_{l=0}^L \Sigma_{sl, i'_E \rightarrow i_E}(\mathbf{x}) \sum_{i'_\Omega=1}^{N_\Omega} w_{i'_\Omega}^\Omega Y_l(\hat{\Omega}_{i_\Omega}, \hat{\Omega}_{i'_\Omega}) \psi_{i'_E, i'_\Omega}(\mathbf{x}) + Q_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\mathbf{x}),$$

$$\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma, \quad i_\Omega \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_\Omega\}, \quad i_E \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_E\},$$
(1)

where $\mathbf{x} = (x, y)$ is a spatial position in the domain Γ ; $\hat{\Omega}_{i_\Omega}$ is the direction the neutron is traveling defined by a vector on the unit sphere for ordinate i_Ω with weight $w_{i_\Omega}^\Omega$; $\Sigma_{t, i_E}(\mathbf{x})$ is the total macroscopic cross section for energy group i_E ; $\Sigma_{sl, i'_E \rightarrow i_E}(\mathbf{x})$ is the l th Legendre moment macroscopic scattering cross section for neutrons scattering from energy group i'_E to i_E ; $\psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\mathbf{x})$ is the neutron angular flux for energy group i_E and ordinate direction i_Ω ; and $Q_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\mathbf{x})$ is the source for energy group i_E and ordinate direction i_Ω . The angular quadrature satisfies $\sum_{i_\Omega=1}^{N_\Omega} w_{i_\Omega}^\Omega = 1$ and we express the spherical harmonics as

$$Y_l(\hat{\Omega}, \hat{\Omega}') = Y_{e,l}^0(\hat{\Omega}) Y_{e,l}^0(\hat{\Omega}') + 2 \sum_{m=1}^l Y_{e,l}^m(\hat{\Omega}) Y_{e,l}^m(\hat{\Omega}'),$$
(2)

where $Y_{e,l}^m(\hat{\Omega})$ is the even spherical harmonic function. In the k -eigenvalue case, the source term is the fission source,

$$Q_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\mathbf{x}) = Q_{i_E}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\chi_{i_E}}{k} \sum_{i'_E=1}^{N_E} \nu \Sigma_{f, i'_E}(\mathbf{x}) \sum_{i'_\Omega=1}^{N_\Omega} w_{i'_\Omega}^\Omega \psi_{i'_E, i'_\Omega}(\mathbf{x}),$$
(3)

with fission spectrum χ_{i_E} , macroscopic fission cross section $\Sigma_{f, i_E}(\mathbf{x})$ for energy group i_E , and average number of neutrons per fission ν . The neutron multiplication factor k makes this system an eigenvalue problem. The scalar flux is

$$\phi_{i_E}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i_\Omega=1}^{N_\Omega} w_{i_\Omega}^\Omega \psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\mathbf{x}).$$
(4)

Assuming quadrant symmetry, the angular quadrature index can be unraveled such that $\hat{\Omega}_{i_\Omega} = \hat{\Omega}_{i_q, i_\mu, i_\gamma} = (\mathbf{c}_{i_q}^\mu \mu_{i_\mu} \mathbf{c}_{i_q}^\eta \sqrt{1 - \mu_{i_\mu}^2} \cos \gamma_{i_\gamma})$ where $\mathbf{c}^\mu = (1, 1, -1, -1)$ and $\mathbf{c}^\eta = (1, -1, 1, -1)$ with $i_q \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, $i_\mu \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_\mu\}$, $i_\gamma \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_\gamma\}$, and $N_\Omega = 4N_\mu N_\gamma$. Additionally, the angular quadrature weight forms a tensor product such that $w_{i_\Omega}^\Omega = w_{i_\mu, i_\gamma}^\Omega = w_{i_\mu}^\mu w_{i_\gamma}^\gamma$.

2.1. Isogeometric Analysis (IGA)

CAD models incorporate multiple *patches* to represent complex geometries having topological differences, varying material properties, or for parallel assembly [1]. Each patch is a spline defined by a set of basis functions, knot vectors, and control points that map the parametric space $\hat{\Gamma}$ to the physical space Γ . A Non-Uniform Rational B-Spline (NURBS) surface with index $i_e \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_e\}$ is defined as

$$\begin{pmatrix} x(\hat{x}, \hat{y}) \\ y(\hat{x}, \hat{y}) \end{pmatrix} = \sum_{i_{\hat{x}}=1}^{N_{\hat{x}}} \sum_{i_{\hat{y}}=1}^{N_{\hat{y}}} R_{i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}}^{p_{\hat{x}}, p_{\hat{y}}}(\hat{x}, \hat{y}) \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{x}_{i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}}^{i_e} \\ \mathbf{y}_{i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}}^{i_e} \end{pmatrix}, \quad R_{i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}}^{p_{\hat{x}}, p_{\hat{y}}}(\hat{x}, \hat{y}) = \frac{A_{i_{\hat{x}}, p_{\hat{x}}}(\hat{x}) B_{i_{\hat{y}}, p_{\hat{y}}}(\hat{y}) \mathbf{w}_{i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}}}{\sum_{i'_{\hat{x}}=1}^{N_{\hat{x}}} \sum_{i'_{\hat{y}}=1}^{N_{\hat{y}}} A_{i'_{\hat{x}}, p_{\hat{x}}}(\hat{x}) B_{i'_{\hat{y}}, p_{\hat{y}}}(\hat{y}) \mathbf{w}_{i'_{\hat{x}}, i'_{\hat{y}}}}, \quad (5)$$

where $R_{i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}}^{p_{\hat{x}}, p_{\hat{y}}}(\hat{x}, \hat{y})$ is a NURBS basis function of degree $p_{\hat{x}}$ and $p_{\hat{y}}$, $\mathbf{x}^{i_e}, \mathbf{y}^{i_e} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\hat{x}} \times N_{\hat{y}}}$ are the control points in the physical space, and $A_{i_{\hat{x}}, p_{\hat{x}}}(\hat{x})$ and $B_{i_{\hat{y}}, p_{\hat{y}}}(\hat{y})$ are B-Spline basis functions of degree $p_{\hat{x}}$ and $p_{\hat{y}}$, respectively, with weights $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\hat{x}} \times N_{\hat{y}}}$. The Cox-de Boor recursion formula gives these B-Spline basis functions,

$$A_{i_{\hat{x}}, p_{\hat{x}}}(\hat{x}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \hat{x}_{i_{\hat{x}}} \leq \hat{x} < \hat{x}_{i_{\hat{x}}}; p_{\hat{x}} = 0 \\ \frac{\hat{x} - \hat{x}_{i_{\hat{x}}}}{\hat{x}_{i_{\hat{x}} + p_{\hat{x}}} - \hat{x}_{i_{\hat{x}}}} A_{i_{\hat{x}}, p_{\hat{x}} - 1}(\hat{x}) + \frac{\hat{x}_{i_{\hat{x}} + p_{\hat{x}} + 1} - \hat{x}}{\hat{x}_{i_{\hat{x}} + p_{\hat{x}} + 1} - \hat{x}_{i_{\hat{x}} + 1}} A_{i_{\hat{x}} + 1, p_{\hat{x}} - 1}(\hat{x}) & p_{\hat{x}} \geq 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is a vector of non-decreasing, potentially repeated real numbers known as the knot vector. In this work, we assume each patch is defined by open knot vectors with only the first and last value repeated $p_{\hat{x}} + 1$ times such that $\hat{\mathbf{x}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\hat{x}} + p_{\hat{x}} + 1}$. The continuity between elements in the vector is $C^{p_{\hat{x}} - 1}$ -continuous with interpolatory end points.

The parametric space is therefore a unit square $\hat{\Gamma}_{i_e} = [0, 1]^2$ discretized into knot spans $[\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i_{\hat{x}}}^u, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{i_{\hat{x}} + 1}^u] \times [\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{i_{\hat{y}}}^u, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{i_{\hat{y}} + 1}^u]$ which map to the physical space Γ_{i_e} by Equation (5). The superscript u denotes only the unique values in $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ with $i_{\hat{x}}^u \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_{\hat{x}} - p_{\hat{x}}\}$ and $i_{\hat{y}}^u \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_{\hat{y}} - p_{\hat{y}}\}$. Numeric integration within a knot span is performed by mapping the span to the parent element space $\tilde{\Gamma}_{i_e}^{i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}} = [-1, 1]^2$ and applying a $(p_{\hat{x}} + 1) \times (p_{\hat{y}} + 1)$ Gaussian quadrature with weights $\mathbf{w}^{\hat{x}} = \left\{ w_{i_{\hat{x}}}^{\hat{x}} w_{i_{\hat{y}}}^{\hat{y}} \right\}_{i_{\hat{x}}=1, i_{\hat{y}}=1}^{p_{\hat{x}}+1, p_{\hat{y}}+1}$.

2.2. Discontinuous Galerkin k -Eigenvalue Neutron Transport Equation

Equation (1) is a semi-continuous integro-differential PDE that now only depends on x . To discretize the spatial component, we apply the Patch Discontinuous Galerkin (PDG) scheme developed in [8]. We multiply Equation (1) by a test function $v(x) \in H^1(\Gamma_{i_e})$ for patch i_e and integrate over the patch. We then apply integration by parts to the streaming term and split the boundary term into inflow $\partial\Gamma_{i_e}^-$ for $\hat{\Omega}_{i_\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n} < 0$ and outflow $\partial\Gamma_{i_e}^+$ for $\hat{\Omega}_{i_\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n} > 0$. For simplicity in notation, we define three inner products: $\{a(\hat{x}), b(\hat{x})\} := \int_{\hat{\Gamma}_{i_e}} a(\hat{x}) b(\hat{x}) |\det \mathbf{J}_{\hat{x}}^{i_e}| d\hat{V}$; $\langle a(\hat{s}), b(\hat{s}) \rangle^- := \int_{\partial\hat{\Gamma}_{i_e}^-} a(\hat{s}) b(\hat{s}) |\hat{\mathbf{x}}'| d\hat{S}$; and $\langle a(\hat{s}), b(\hat{s}) \rangle^+ :=$

$\int_{\partial\hat{\Gamma}_e^+} a(\hat{s})b(\hat{s})|\hat{\mathbf{x}}'|d\hat{S}$. The resulting system is then

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle (\hat{\mathbf{\Omega}}_{i_\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n})v(\hat{s}), \psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\hat{s}) \rangle^+ - \hat{\mathbf{\Omega}}_{i_E} \cdot \{ (\mathbf{J}_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}}^{i_E})^{-1} \nabla_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}} v(\hat{\mathbf{x}}), \psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) \} + \Sigma_{t, i_E} \{ v(\hat{\mathbf{x}}), \psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) \} \\ & = \sum_{i'_E=1}^{N_E} \sum_{l=0}^L \Sigma_{sl, i'_E \rightarrow i_E} \sum_{i'_\Omega=1}^{N_\Omega} w_{i'_\Omega}^\Omega Y_l(\hat{\mathbf{\Omega}}_{i_E}, \hat{\mathbf{\Omega}}_{i'_E}) \{ v(\hat{\mathbf{x}}), \psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) \} \\ & + \{ v(\hat{\mathbf{x}}), Q_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\mathbf{x}) \} + \langle |\hat{\mathbf{\Omega}}_{i_\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n}| v(\hat{s}), \psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}^{adj}(\hat{s}) \rangle^-, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}}^{i_E}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) : \hat{\Gamma}_{i_E} \rightarrow \Gamma_{i_E}$, \mathbf{n} is the outward normal vector, and $\psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}^{adj}(\hat{s})$ is the incident flux from adjacent patches or boundary conditions.

We seek a solution $\psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\mathbf{x}) \in H^1(\Gamma_{i_E})$ such that Equation (7) holds $\forall v(\mathbf{x}) \in H^1(\Gamma_{i_E})$. Using the isoparametric concept, we assert that the solution and test function have the same form as the NURBS defining the geometry,

$$v(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_{i_{\hat{x}}=1}^{N_{\hat{x}}} \sum_{i_{\hat{y}}=1}^{N_{\hat{y}}} R_{i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}}^{p_{\hat{x}}, p_{\hat{y}}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) \mathbf{v}_{i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}} = \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{v}, \quad \psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) = \sum_{i_{\hat{x}}=1}^{N_{\hat{x}}} \sum_{i_{\hat{y}}=1}^{N_{\hat{y}}} R_{i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}}^{p_{\hat{x}}, p_{\hat{y}}}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) \Psi_{i_E, i_\Omega, i_{\hat{x}}, i_{\hat{y}}} = \mathbf{R}^T \Psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{R} is a vector of NURBS basis functions of shape $N_{\hat{x}} N_{\hat{y}} \times 1$ with control variables \mathbf{v} , $\Psi_{i_E, i_\Omega} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\hat{x}} N_{\hat{y}} \times 1}$. The resulting system of $N_\Omega \times N_E \times N_{\hat{x}} \times N_{\hat{y}}$ linear equations for patch i_e is

$$\mathcal{H}\Psi + \mathcal{B}_{out}\Psi = \mathcal{S}\Psi + \frac{1}{k}\mathcal{F}\Psi + \mathcal{B}_{in}\Psi, \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathcal{H}\Psi)_{i_E, i_\Omega} &= \Sigma_{t, i_E} \{ \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{R}^T \} \Psi_{i_E, i_\Omega} - \hat{\mathbf{\Omega}}_{i_\Omega} \cdot \{ (\mathbf{J}_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}}^{i_E})^{-1} \nabla_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}} \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{R}^T \} \Psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}, \\ (\mathcal{S}\Psi)_{i_E, i_\Omega} &= \sum_{i'_E=1}^{N_E} \sum_{l=0}^L \Sigma_{sl, i'_E \rightarrow i_E} \sum_{i'_\Omega=1}^{N_\Omega} w_{i'_\Omega}^\Omega Y_l(\hat{\mathbf{\Omega}}_{i_\Omega}, \hat{\mathbf{\Omega}}_{i'_E}) \{ \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{R}^T \} \Psi_{i'_E, i'_\Omega}, \quad (\mathcal{B}_{in}\Psi)_{i_E, i_\Omega} = \langle |\hat{\mathbf{\Omega}}_{i_\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n}| \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{R}^T \rangle^- \Psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}^{adj}, \\ & \quad (\mathcal{B}_{out}\Psi)_{i_E, i_\Omega} = \langle (\hat{\mathbf{\Omega}}_{i_\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n}) \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{R}^T \rangle^+ \Psi_{i_E, i_\Omega}, \\ (\mathcal{F}\Psi)_{i_E, i_\Omega} &= \chi_{i_E} \sum_{i'_E=1}^{N_E} \nu \Sigma_{f, i'_E} \sum_{i'_\Omega=1}^{N_\Omega} \{ \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{R}^T \} \Psi_{i'_E, i'_\Omega}, \end{aligned}$$

where \mathcal{H} is the streaming and collision operator, \mathcal{S} is the scattering operator, \mathcal{F} is the fission operator, \mathcal{B}_{in} is the inflow boundary operator, and \mathcal{B}_{out} is the outflow boundary operator.

2.3. Tensor Train (TT) Decomposition

A d -dimensional tensor $\mathcal{T} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_1 \times N_2 \times \dots \times N_D}$ has exponential in d memory complexity, $\mathcal{O}(N^d)$. This property is called the *curse of dimensionality*, which may be mitigated by a tensor network decomposition. The tensor train (TT) decomposition [5] approximately factorizes a d -dimensional tensor into the linear contraction network of d 3-dimensional tensors. For $2d$ -dimensional operators, the factorization results in a linear network of d 4-dimensional tensors,

$$\mathcal{A}(i_1, i'_1, i_2, i'_2, \dots, i_d, i'_d) = \sum_{\alpha_1=1}^{r_1} \sum_{\alpha_2=1}^{r_2} \dots \sum_{\alpha_d=1}^{r_d} \mathcal{G}_1(1, i_1, i'_1, \alpha_1) \mathcal{G}_2(\alpha_1, i_2, i'_2, \alpha_2) \dots \mathcal{G}_d(\alpha_d, i_d, i'_d, 1), \quad (10)$$

where $\mathcal{G}_j \in \mathbb{R}^{r_{j-1} \times N_j \times N_j \times r_j}$ is the j th TT-core with TT-ranks $r_j \in \{1, r_1, r_2, \dots, r_d, 1\}$. This decomposition is the result of successive singular value decompositions in the TT-SVD algorithm [5]. To build a low rank representation for the full tensor $\mathcal{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_1^2 \times N_2^2 \times \dots \times N_d^2}$ we truncate the TT-ranks such that $\|\tilde{\mathcal{A}} - \mathcal{A}\|_F \leq \epsilon \|\mathcal{A}\|_F$ where $\|\cdot\|_F$ is the Frobenius norm, $\tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ is the truncated tensor train decomposition, and ϵ is some acceptable error. The resulting low-rank representation has $\mathcal{O}(dNr^2)$ memory complexity and supports linear algebra operations analogous to those for matrices and vectors.

3. METHODS

We implement the operators in Equation (9) in both the TT and Compressed Sparse Row (CSR) formats for comparison. For brevity, we defer the details of the assembly procedure to our recent work [9]; however, all work shown in this paper can be found on our repository [ttnte](https://github.com/myerspat/ttnte)¹ and follows similarly to [3]. The resulting operators are shape $[4 \times N_\mu \times N_\gamma \times N_E \times N_e \times N_{\hat{x}} \times N_{\hat{y}}]^2$. We note that only the spatial components of \mathcal{S}^{CSR} and \mathcal{F}^{CSR} are CSR, with the energy and angular components applied separately for memory considerations. We then can combine \mathcal{H}^{CSR} , \mathcal{B}_{in}^{CSR} , and \mathcal{B}_{out}^{CSR} but treat \mathcal{S}^{CSR} and \mathcal{F}^{CSR} separately. The TT operators may be combined and recompressed using the TT-rounding algorithm [5]. The cases we explore here are then

$$\text{CSR: } (\mathcal{H}^{CSR} + \mathcal{B}_{out}^{CSR} - \mathcal{B}_{in}^{CSR})\Psi - \mathcal{S}^{CSR}\Psi = \frac{1}{k}\mathcal{F}^{CSR}\Psi, \quad (11a)$$

$$\text{TT: } (\mathcal{H}^{TT} - \mathcal{S}^{TT} + \mathcal{B}_{out}^{TT} - \mathcal{B}_{in}^{TT})\Psi = \frac{1}{k}\mathcal{F}^{TT}\Psi, \quad (11b)$$

$$\text{Mixed: } (\mathcal{H}^{TT} - \mathcal{S}^{TT})\Psi + (\mathcal{B}_{out}^{CSR} - \mathcal{B}_{in}^{CSR})\Psi = \frac{1}{k}\mathcal{F}^{TT}\Psi, \quad (11c)$$

where Ψ is a full vector. The TT operators that are summed together are rounded to a truncation error ϵ . Each TT operator is applied to Ψ at cost $\mathcal{O}(dr^2N^d \log(N))$ while the CSR operators are $\mathcal{O}(nnz)$.

We use power iteration over the fission source and unpreconditioned restarted GMRES to solve the resulting linear system, inverting the left-hand side of Equation (11). We save the GMRES extension with a tensorized multilevel preconditioner for future work.

4. APPLICATIONS

In this section, we present two applications: a single group homogenized critical circle [10] and an infinite array of cruciform fuel with seven-group KAIST cross sections [11]. All TT decompositions use $\epsilon = 10^{-5}$. The compression ratio of a TT or CSR matrix is

$$\text{CR} = \frac{\text{\# of elements in the full tensor}}{\text{\# of elements in the TT or CSR representation}}. \quad (12)$$

Both applications use power iteration with a convergence criterion of $\|\Psi^{(m+1)} - \Psi^{(m)}\|_2 < 10^{-8}\|\Psi^{(m)}\|_2$ for iteration index m . Each iteration is solved with restarted GMRES with a convergence criterion of $\|\mathbf{r}\|_2 < 10^{-10} \left\| \frac{1}{k^{(m)}} \mathcal{F}\Psi^{(m)} \right\|_2$ where \mathbf{r} is the residual. All results were generated on a cluster with a 64-core AMD Ryzen Threadripper PRO processor, an NVIDIA RTX PRO 6000 Blackwell Max-Q GPU, and 512 GB of RAM. We run the power iteration, GMRES, and operator-vector products on the GPU.

4.1. Homogenized Circular Domain

Our first application is a homogenized critical circle from [10]. This is an analytic benchmark with a critical radius of $r_c = 4.279960 \text{ cm}$ and single group cross sections $\Sigma_t = 0.32640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\nu\Sigma_f = 2.84 \cdot 0.081600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\Sigma_{s0} = 0.225216 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. We discretize the NTE operators with $N_\Omega = 4096$ ordinates, $N_e = 1$ patch, and $N_{\hat{x}} \times N_{\hat{y}} = 196$ control variables for a NURBS surface patch of degree $p_{\hat{x}} = p_{\hat{y}} = 4$ and $N_{\hat{x}} = N_{\hat{y}} = 14$. The resulting system has $N_\Omega \times N_e \times N_{\hat{x}} \times N_{\hat{y}} = 802,816$ degrees of freedom. GMRES uses 5 restarts with 30 iterations. The benchmark provides two analytic reference solutions for the scalar flux in polar coordinates $\phi^{ref}(r)$, $\phi^{ref}(0.5r_c)/(\phi^{ref}(0)) = 0.8093$ and $\phi^{ref}(r_c)/(\phi^{ref}(0)) =$

¹<https://github.com/myerspat/ttnte>

Table I. Compression ratios (CRs) and tensor train (TT) ranks for TT and Compressed Sparse Row (CSR) formats for the homogenized circle and infinite array of cruciform fuel applications. Note that "Total" is the left-hand side of Equations (11a) and (11b) and "Total (Mixed)" is the same for Equation (11c).

Operator	Homogenized Circle			Infinite Array of Cruciform Fuel		
	TT-Ranks	TT CR	CSR CR	TT-Ranks	TT CR	CSR CR
\mathcal{H}	{3, 3, 3, 22}	1.804×10^7	6.942×10^3	{3, 3, 3, 5, 22, 9}	3.006×10^9	2.984×10^5
\mathcal{S}	{1, 1, 1, 7}	1.341×10^8	1.514×10^7	{3, 3, 2, 3, 9, 5}	1.005×10^{10}	5.243×10^5
\mathcal{F}	{1, 1, 1, 7}	1.341×10^8	1.675×10^7	{1, 1, 1, 1, 3, 4}	4.631×10^{10}	1.049×10^6
\mathcal{B}_{in}	—	—	—	{8, 38, 89, 93, 50, 4}	7.490×10^7	5.156×10^6
\mathcal{B}_{out}	{4, 66, 49, 29}	1.667×10^5	2.369×10^5	{4, 34, 85, 89, 47, 3}	8.675×10^7	5.181×10^6
Total	{5, 66, 48, 41}	1.621×10^5	6.938×10^3	{9, 41, 84, 87, 113, 13}	5.177×10^7	1.862×10^5
Total (Mixed)	{4, 4, 3, 21}	2.330×10^5		{6, 6, 5, 5, 22, 9}	3.261×10^6	

Table II. Metrics and solution time for the homogeneous circle with Equation (11). Errors use $\delta k = k - 1$ and Equation (13).

Case	CSR	TT	Mixed
Time (s)	60.750	6082.215	138.541
δk (pcm)	-0.370	-0.442	-0.392
$\epsilon_2(0.5r_c)$	3.201×10^{-4}	3.205×10^{-4}	3.200×10^{-4}
$\epsilon_2(r_c)$	7.893×10^{-3}	7.893×10^{-3}	7.894×10^{-3}

Figure 1. Solution for the homogenized circle.

0.2926, which we use with an L2-error,

$$\epsilon_2(r) = \frac{\phi^{ref}(0)}{\phi^{ref}(0)} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \left(\frac{\phi(r, \theta)}{\phi(0, \theta)} - \frac{\phi^{ref}(r)}{\phi^{ref}(0)} \right)^2 d\theta}. \quad (13)$$

Table I shows the compression ratios for the operators in CSR and TT formats. Note that there is no compression ratio for the inflow boundary operator, as there is only one patch and all vacuum boundary conditions. There are adequate low-rank TT representations for interior operators (\mathcal{H} , \mathcal{S} , and \mathcal{F}) with $CR > 10^7$. In contrast, the outgoing boundary operator is two orders of magnitude lower due to the high coupling between the direction and the curvilinear boundaries. The mixed approach in Equation (11c) proves to be the best approach for CR.

Error metrics and time to solution are presented in Table II. The error is consistent across all three cases in Equation (11), with minor discrepancies. In all cases, the eigenvalue is within 1 pcm of the critical value. While the TT cases show considerably more compression, the time to solution of CSR is 100× and 2.28× faster than the TT and Mixed cases, respectively. This is due to the use of a full solution vector, which does not optimally exploit the low-rank TT structure in the operator-vector product. However, decomposing the angular flux into the TT format gives ranks {4, 127, 191, 14} and $CR = 0.967 < 1$, meaning it is not compressible in the TT format. We show the solution for the CSR case in Figure 1.

4.2. Infinite Array of Cruciform Fuel

Figure 2a shows the quarter geometry of a four-lobe cruciform fuel pin similar to published designs by Lightbridge. We use reflective boundary conditions for all boundaries. For this application, we use the seven-group KAIST cross sections [11] with linearly anisotropic scattering. We generated a reference OpenMC solution with a regular mesh of cell-averaged scalar fluxes $\phi^{ref}, \sigma^{ref} \in \mathbb{R}^{7 \times 128 \times 128}$, where

Table III. Solution times and error metrics for the infinite array of cruciform fuel problem. We define $\delta k = k - k^{ref}$ and the scalar flux error metric by Equation (14).

Case	Time (h)	δk (pcm)	ϵ_1^1 (pcm)	ϵ_2^2 (pcm)	ϵ_3^3 (pcm)	ϵ_4^4 (pcm)	ϵ_5^5 (pcm)	ϵ_6^6 (pcm)	ϵ_7^7 (pcm)	ϵ_2 (pcm)
CSR	4.86	-22.61	399.8	71.66	67.82	87.79	86.82	76.11	106.7	449.5
Mixed	22.54	-21.11	399.8	71.64	67.86	87.86	86.87	75.63	106.0	449.2

Figure 2. Cruciform problem where (a) shows the geometry with the black lines indicating patch boundaries; (b) is the scalar flux solution for the first energy group; and (c) is the scalar flux solution for the last energy group.

σ^{ref} is the standard deviation in each cell, and $k^{ref} = 1.25669 \pm 0.00007$. GMRES uses 10 restarts with 75 iterations. We use a discretization of $N_\Omega = 1024$, $N_E = 7$, $N_e = 12$, $N_{\hat{x}} = 12$, and $N_{\hat{y}} = 12$ resulting in 12,386,304 degrees of freedom. Each patch is degree $p_{\hat{x}} = p_{\hat{y}} = 2$. In this application, we do not solve Equation (11b) because it performed poorly in the previous application.

The compression ratios and TT ranks for the operators are shown in Table I. Again, all interior operators are two to three orders of magnitude higher than the boundary operators for the TT format. All TT operators are more compressed than their CSR counterparts. The most compressed total operator is the one with all operators summed and rounded in TT format, followed by Mixed and CSR.

To evaluate our method, we use an L2 error metric,

$$\epsilon_2^{i_E} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i_x=1}^{128} \sum_{i_y=1}^{128} (\phi_{i_E, i_x, i_y} - \phi_{i_E, i_x, i_y}^{ref})^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i_x=1}^{128} \sum_{i_y=1}^{128} (\phi_{i_E, i_x, i_y}^{ref})^2}}, \quad \epsilon_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i_E}^{N_E} (\epsilon_2^{i_E})^2}, \quad (14)$$

for each group i_E where $\phi \in \mathbb{R}^{7 \times 128 \times 128}$ is our solution $\phi(\hat{x}, \hat{y})$ averaged onto the same regular mesh. The results are shown in Table III along with eigenvalue error and time-to-solution. The errors match closely between CSR and Mixed; however, their deviations from OpenMC are statistically significant, with a minimum of -29σ , a maximum of 21σ , a mean of -0.0674σ , and a median of -0.0297σ . We note that the maximum standard deviation in a cell is 0.110% of the scalar flux. Additionally, based on the time-to-solution, power iteration with unpreconditioned GMRES struggled with this problem, necessitating a preconditioner. Both CSR and Mixed required 963 and 854 power iterations, respectively, with the GMRES solver failing to converge. Compressing the angular flux in the TT format gives TT-ranks of $\{4, 64, 795, 1031, 144, 12\}$ and $CR = 1.482$, which is slightly compressible in the TT format. We show the scalar flux for the first and seventh energy groups in Figures 2b and 2c, respectively.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Both applications achieved higher compression ratios in the TT format than in the Compressed Sparse Row (CSR) sparse matrix format, particularly for interior operators. However, TT operators suffered in operator-matrix products due to the unfavorable scaling of $\mathcal{O}(dr^2N^d \log(N))$ compared to $\mathcal{O}(nnz)$ for CSR. Future work includes adding a tensorized GMRES preconditioner and exploring a general tensor network decomposition suitable for the solution vector to reduce TT solution times.

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